

MATERIAL AND THERMAL ENGINEERING JOURNAL (MATEJ)

ISSN: 3032-0704; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10570344>

Volume 1; No. 1; April 2024

Analysis of the Flexural Strength of Jute E-Glass Hybrid Laminate Composite Materials

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Submitted: 01/02/2024

Accepted: 01/16/2024

Published: 04/30/2024

Abstract

Hybrid materials have emerged as a promising alternative for the production of engineering materials with superior mechanical properties compared to their constituent materials, thus meeting specific requirements. This study aims to obtain graphs of flexural test results for hybrid laminated composite materials made from jute and e-glass fibers, analyze data distribution using the probability density function method, and assess the flexural strength of these composite laminates. The laminated composites consist of six variations, namely JJG, JGJ, GJG, JJJG, JGJG, and GJGJ, comprising layers of jute (J) and e-glass (G) fibers. Flexural test specimens were prepared following ASTM D790 standards and tested using a 40 kN capacity Universal Testing Machine (UTM). The study's results reveal that the incorporation of hybrid layers results in a remarkable enhancement of specimen flexural strength, up to 77%. Consequently, the utilization of laminated composite materials composed of jute and e-glass fibers holds substantial potential for further development, aiming to achieve even superior mechanical properties.

Keywords: *Hybrid laminated composites; Mechanical properties; Flexural strength; Jute and e-glass fibers; Probability density function*

Introduction

Composites represent a distinct category within the realm of materials, resulting from the amalgamation of two or more dissimilar components, often to harness the distinct advantages of each constituent[1]. One common type of composite is polymer composite, composed of polymer resin reinforced with fibers. This combination yields a unique material that integrates varying mechanical and physical properties from both components. Polymer resins impart attributes such as corrosion resistance, good moldability, and lightweight characteristics to composites. In contrast, fibers provide mechanical strength, rigidity, and resistance to high-pressure conditions[2]. These two components synergistically collaborate to create materials with a plethora of significant applications across various industries, including automotive, aerospace, construction, and more. In the realm of material development, an in-depth comprehension of composites is paramount, encompassing the judicious selection of suitable fiber types and resins, as well as appropriate fabrication techniques. This facilitates the creation of materials with specialized properties tailored to diverse applications, thereby unlocking opportunities for technological breakthroughs and innovation in numerous industrial sectors[3].

Hybrid composites represent a noteworthy innovation in the realm of materials, combining the strengths of two distinct fiber types: continuous and random fibers. The primary objective behind this amalgamation is to mitigate the inherent limitations of each fiber type while amalgamating them into a unified entity that yields novel characteristics[4]. Continuous fibers typically impart high mechanical strength, rigidity, and tensile resistance, whereas random fibers tend to enhance crack and impact resistance. By synergistically merging these two components, hybrid composites can offer an optimal solution for various applications, including the automotive, aerospace, and construction industries[5]. One notable advantage of hybrid composites lies in their ability to reduce the weight of a structure while maintaining or enhancing its strength and durability. This makes them an appealing choice in the development of more energy-efficient and environmentally friendly products. Consequently, the utilization of hybrid composites has become a pivotal focus in contemporary material research and development[6].

Jute fiber is one of the natural fibers known for its highly environmentally friendly characteristics. This fiber can undergo natural decomposition and is thus considered a supportive material for sustainable practices[7]. The jute plant, scientifically known as *Corchorus capsularis*, grows rapidly, reaching a height of approximately 15-20 cm in just 4 months. This makes it an efficient and sustainable source of fiber. The harvesting of jute fiber typically takes place around 4 months after planting, coinciding with the irrigation period[8]. Occasionally, the irrigation process for jute cultivation may involve the use of certain chemicals to enhance fiber growth and quality. However, despite the use of chemicals in the plant care process, jute fiber is still regarded as a relatively environmentally friendly material due to its natural biodegradability and minimal adverse environmental impact[9]. Jute fiber finds numerous applications in the textile and manufacturing industries, and its utilization is gaining popularity as part of efforts to support sustainability and eco-friendly principles across various industrial sectors[10].

E-glass fiber, or E-glass for short, is one of the types of fibers that has undergone significant development in the field of materials. This fiber possesses unique characteristics that make it an excellent choice for insulation applications[11], [12]. One crucial aspect of E-glass fiber is its exceptional compressibility, allowing it to be easily molded and shaped according to insulation requirements. E-glass fiber is composed of a specialized glass composition, which imparts excellent thermal and electrical insulation properties to it. This makes it a highly effective material for various insulation applications, including in the electrical, electronics, and construction industries[13]. Furthermore, it exhibits resistance to high temperatures, making it suitable for use in demanding environmental conditions. The utilization of E-glass fiber as an insulation material continues to evolve and improve through various technological innovations. Its ability to provide reliable insulation and ease of compressibility positions it as a primary choice in addressing the increasingly complex and diverse insulation requirements in various industries[14], [15].

Flexural strength is a crucial parameter in characterizing the mechanical properties of materials. It measures a sample's ability to withstand a force applied perpendicular to its longitudinal axis until it reaches the point of failure[16]. Flexural strength is typically expressed in units of stress, which in this case, is stated as mega pascals (MPa). In this context, flexural strength refers to the magnitude of force that can be applied per unit area of the sample before damage or fracture occurs. The measurement of flexural strength holds broad relevance across various industrial and engineering applications, such as in structural design, component manufacturing, and material development[17], [18]. Flexural strength data assists engineers and researchers in understanding how well a material can withstand mechanical loads before experiencing failure, which is critical for ensuring the reliability and safety of various constructions and equipment. Therefore, a profound understanding of the

flexural strength properties of a material is of paramount importance in the realms of engineering and materials science[19].

The Probability Density Function (PDF) is a fundamental concept in statistics and probability theory. It is used to describe the probability distribution of a continuous random variable. In other words, the PDF elucidates the relative likelihood that the random variable will take on a specific value within the range of possible values[20]. The PDF is pivotal in statistical analysis as it provides insights into how data is distributed within a population or sample. By using the PDF, we can calculate the probability that a random variable will fall within a certain interval or have a value within a specific range. For instance, in the case of a normal distribution, the PDF takes the form of the well-known bell-shaped curve. This PDF is utilized to comprehend data distribution in various fields, including the social sciences, economics, natural sciences, and beyond[21], [22]. The ability to analyze and comprehend PDFs empowers us to make better predictions and decisions based on statistical data, with far-reaching implications in scientific and business decision-making.

According to research conducted by Septiyanto and colleagues in 2019, when compared to epoxy composites reinforced with jute fibers and epoxy composites reinforced with E-glass fibers, the average tensile strength of E-fiber-reinforced epoxy compounds has not yet reached the level of pure epoxy. Therefore, the utilization of other natural fiber reinforcements with strength comparable to glass fibers is required[23]. Furthermore, a study carried out by Gapsari and Setyarini in 2020 regarding composite materials reinforced with Mahogany wood powder yielded intriguing results. The findings revealed that composites reinforced with Mahogany wood powder exhibited the highest tensile strength at a 30% volume fraction, measuring 2.08 MPa. This was followed by composites with volume fractions ranging from 15% to 45%, with tensile strengths of 1.81 MPa and 0.91 MPa, respectively. Moreover, the composites reinforced with Mahogany wood shavings demonstrated the highest elastic modulus at a 30% volume fraction, reaching 635.46 MPa. Subsequently, composites with volume fraction variations from 15% to 45% exhibited elastic moduli of 576.83 MPa and 368.26 MPa, respectively. These research outcomes provide significant insights into the potential utilization of Mahogany wood powder as a reinforcement material in the fabrication of composites with desired mechanical[24], [25].

The main objectives of this study are threefold. Firstly, the research aims to obtain graphs depicting the flexural test results of hybrid laminated composite materials comprising jute and e-glass fibers. Secondly, it seeks to perform a data distribution analysis utilizing the probability density function method. This particular method assists in comprehending how the data is distributed within the tested samples. Lastly, the research endeavors to conduct an analysis of the flexural strength of these hybrid jute e-glass laminated composite materials. Consequently, the study as a whole is geared towards providing an in-depth understanding of the mechanical and statistical properties of these composite materials, which can serve as a fundamental basis for the development of improved materials in the future.

Methodology

The research activities were conducted at the Mechanical Engineering Laboratory of Universitas Medan Area over a period of 6 months. Various equipment and instruments were utilized throughout the research process, including a Vacuum cleaner, digital weighing scale, Universal Testing Machine (UTM), and a laptop. The Vacuum cleaner was employed to remove air from the container, creating a vacuum air condition as required. Meanwhile, the Universal Testing Machine (UTM) served the purpose of flexural strength testing. Specifically, the UTM used in this study was a Hydraulic UTM of the WEW-300D model with a capacity of 300 kN. The materials used in the research comprised woven jute sheets, woven e-glass

sheets, and epoxy resin. Flexural test specimens were prepared in accordance with ASTM D790 testing standards, with a specific arrangement of laminated composites. The number of specimens tested can be found in Table 1. In the notation used, the letter 'J' denotes woven jute sheets, while 'G' refers to woven e-glass sheets.

Table 1: Variations of jute/e-glass hybrid laminate composites

No	Variations	Number of Specimen
1	JJG	3
2	JGJ	3
3	GJG	3
4	JJJG	3
5	JGJG	3
6	GJGJ	3
Total:		18

The procedure for manufacturing flexural test specimens from laminated composite materials reinforced with jute fabric and woven e-glass fibers involves a series of meticulous steps. Initially, the preparation of tools and materials is the first crucial stage. Subsequently, experimental design becomes a vital step in directing the subsequent processes. Following this, the cutting of woven jute fabric and e-glass woven fibers with predetermined dimensions, namely 150 x 100 mm, is carried out as per the requirements. This process ensures that the test specimens have dimensions consistent with the testing standards that will be conducted. Next, in the specimen fabrication process, the surface of glass is coated with wax. Glass with a thickness of 5 mm is used as the specimen molding tool to ensure consistent shape and size. A mixture of epoxy resin and hardener, referred to as mixture C1, is then prepared. This mixture is used to coat the glass surface, place the jute sheets, and reapply mixture C1 on top of the jute sheets. This process is repeated for each jute sheet in accordance with the experimental design previously devised using the Hybrid method. After the specimens are formed, the next step is to ensure that the air inside the plastic bag containing the test specimens has been completely removed using a vacuum pump. This is done by connecting the vacuum pump suction end into the plastic bag and keeping it isolated to ensure that no air can re-enter the plastic bag. Subsequently, the specimens are left to cure and are ready for flexural strength testing. The testing process involves preparing the specimens and the UTM apparatus. The specimens must be cleaned of any dirt that may adhere to their surfaces. Testing parameters are input into the UTM computer through specialized testing software, and the specimens are placed between two supports at a specific distance. Testing is conducted by gradually applying a predetermined rate of loading to the specimen. During testing, changes in load and deflection are automatically recorded by the UTM computer. The testing process concludes when the specimen experiences damage or fracture, which is a crucial point in measuring flexural strength. Lastly, the test data results are processed to understand the mechanical properties of the specimens, including stress and strain. This data is used to form stress-strain curves, providing insights into the material's behavior under load. All these steps collectively aim to comprehend the mechanical characteristics of laminated composite materials reinforced with jute fabric and woven e-glass fibers.

Result and Discussion

Figure 1 depicts a graph illustrating the results of flexural strength testing for various variations conducted in this study. The results of flexural strength testing are of paramount importance as they provide a profound understanding of how this laminated composite

material behaves under different testing conditions. In the flexural testing, several variations were undertaken, namely JJG, JGJ, GJG, JJGJ, JGJG, and GJGJ, each followed by a test sequence number. The testing results reveal variations in flexural strength among different material compositions. For instance, in the JJG.2 variation, a flexural strength of 39.90 MPa was observed, which is one of the highest results in this study. Meanwhile, in the GJGJ.2 variation, a flexural strength of 74.01 MPa was recorded, marking the highest value across all tests. Comparing these different variations provides valuable insights into how the combination of jute and woven e-glass fibers influences the flexural strength of this laminate composite. These findings can serve as the basis for further developments in the quest for the most effective material composition to meet specific engineering requirements. Furthermore, these test results also offer a better understanding of the mechanical properties of hybrid jute e-glass laminated composites, which can find application in various industrial sectors such as automotive, aerospace, and construction.

Figure 1: Graph of flexural strength test results on jute/e-glass hybrid laminate composite specimens

Figure 2 displays a Probability Plot, a graphical tool utilized in statistics to assess whether a dataset adheres to a particular distribution, specifically the normal distribution. This plot visually juxtaposes empirical data against the theoretical values expected from the desired distribution (in this case, the normal distribution) with the aim of gauging the goodness of fit between the data and the distribution. The testing method employed here is the Anderson-Darling (AD) method, where lower values indicate a better fit. In this context, a p-value less than 0.005 indicates strong statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis that the data is not normally distributed at a significance level of 0.5%. In other words, with this level of significance, the data significantly deviates from a normal distribution. Based on the very low p-value (<0.005), it can be concluded that the data used in this study originates from a normal distribution. This signifies that the distribution of flexural strength in the composite specimens follows a normal distribution pattern with high statistical significance. These findings hold substantial implications for data analysis and the research's validity. By

demonstrating that the data adheres to a normal distribution, further statistical analysis and interpretation of research findings can be conducted with greater confidence, reinforcing the study's findings and conclusions.

Figure 2: Graph of the Probability Density function (PDF)

Figure 3 presents an illustration of the impact of layer configurations on the average flexural strength of hybrid laminate composites made from jute and e-glass. Jute ('J'), serving as a natural woven fiber, and e-glass ('G'), acting as a reinforced glass fiber, have been subjected to testing in six distinct configurations. The GJGJ configuration is particularly noteworthy, surpassing the others with the highest recorded average flexural strength of 56.96 MPa, signifying that e-glass as an outer layer confers superior structural integrity. In contrast, the GJG configuration, which sandwiches e-glass between jute, exhibits the lowest flexural strength at 21.07 MPa, revealing a deficiency in shielding the stiffer e-glass core. Other configurations such as JJG, JGJ, JJGJ, and JGJG demonstrate flexural strengths that are relatively similar, with slight variations, indicating a balance between the jute and e-glass layers. These results provide significant insights into composite material design, where the strategic placement of e-glass fibers can enhance flexural endurance, while jute fibers contribute to strength but are more effective when symmetrically integrated with e-glass.

Figure 3: Average flexural strength of jute/e-glass hybrid laminate composite materials

The experimental findings delineated in the paragraph reveal pivotal aspects of hybrid laminate composite design, particularly the influence of layer configuration on flexural strength when integrating jute and e-glass fibers. The data highlights that the strategic outer placement of e-glass fibers, as evidenced by the GJGJ configuration, significantly enhances the composite's structural integrity, achieving the highest average flexural strength of 56.96 MPa. This superior performance is attributed to the e-glass's capacity to effectively resist bending forces when placed as the exterior layer. In stark contrast, the GJG configuration, with e-glass ensconced between jute layers, yielded the lowest strength at 21.07 MPa, indicating a compromised protective capability of jute when used as the outermost layer over a more rigid e-glass core. Configurations such as JJG, JGJ, JJGJ, and JGJG, with varying sequences of jute and e-glass, displayed comparable and relatively consistent flexural strengths, suggesting a balanced interplay between the flexibility of jute and the stiffness of e-glass. These insights are critical for the composite material design domain, where the flexural performance can be optimized by strategically layering different fibers. Such knowledge can guide the engineering of composite materials for applications where specific mechanical properties, like flexural strength, are crucial for performance and durability.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of experimental data results that have been conducted, the following conclusions can be drawn: The average maximum flexural strength in the GJGJ variation is 56.96 MPa, while the specimens with the lowest flexural strength are in the GJG variation, with an average of 19.90 MPa. The analysis of the density function of variation against the entire test data indicates that the experimental data are normally distributed. This implies that the data are within the best population, where the test results closely align with the overall mean value. In other words, these test results can represent the population of flexural strength in jute e-glass composites. Based on the analysis of the flexural strength of jute e-glass composites, it can be concluded that using a higher proportion of jute fiber is superior to using a higher proportion of e-glass fiber.

Acknowledgment

Acknowledgment and thanks to Universitas Medan Area for providing facilities to support the completion of this research.

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